

Exploration of the experience of fatigue in schizophrenia in a psychosocial rehabilitation
context

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ABSTRACT

Background: Fatigue is a highly prevalent and disabling symptom in schizophrenia, affecting approximately 60% of patients. Despite its impact on quality of life and rehabilitation outcomes, the lived experience of fatigue in this population remains unexplored. This qualitative study aimed to explore the lived experience of fatigue in people with schizophrenia engaged in a psychosocial rehabilitation programme, their ability to differentiate fatigue from symptoms with close constructs, and the perceived causes of fatigue.

Methods: Twelve semi-structured interviews were conducted with participants with schizophrenia. Descriptive generic qualitative approach was applied, using inductive content analysis. Fatigue severity was measured using the Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI-20). Clinical assessments included the PANSS and GAF scales.

Results: A total of 598 meaning units were identified and organised into three classifications: experience of fatigue, perceived causes, and differentiation from other symptoms. Fatigue manifested primarily through sensations of heaviness, effort, and need for sleep, and was described as persistent and severe (mean MFI-20 total score: 68.4 ± 16.6 , 90th population percentile). Fatigue represented a major barrier to daily activities. Antipsychotic medication, schizophrenia itself, and both activity and inactivity were the most frequently cited causes for fatigue. Management strategies included energy restoration, distraction, and pacing. Participants differentiated fatigue and symptoms such as amotivation, sedation, and depression on a conceptual level, yet reported difficulties in dissociating them.

Conclusion: Fatigue in schizophrenia is persistent, severe, and multidimensional, constituting a barrier to psychosocial rehabilitation. Interoceptive difficulties complexify its identification and management. Interventions combining physical activity, pacing strategies, and psychoeducation targeting fatigue catastrophism and interoceptive awareness should be investigated.

Keywords: schizophrenia; fatigue; qualitative research; psychosocial rehabilitation; interoception; lived experience

INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a severe mental illness affecting about one percent of the population worldwide (Tréhout & Dollfus, 2018). The illness manifests through several symptoms, usually divided into three categories: positive symptoms, such as hallucinations and delusions, negative symptoms such as anhedonia, poverty of speech or fatigue, and cognitive symptoms, manifesting through altered cognitive function (e.g. attention deficits or memory difficulties) (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). To this day, the illness is mainly treated through antipsychotics to manage positive symptoms (Stępnicki et al., 2018). However, antipsychotics can induce adverse effects, such as metabolic disturbances and aggravation of cognitive and negative symptoms (Singh et al., 2019).

Amongst negative symptoms, fatigue, that can be defined as a symptom or a sign manifesting through difficulties to uphold cognitive and/or physical labour (Micklewright et al., 2017), has a negative impact on patients' daily lives. As a symptom, fatigue is highly prevalent in schizophrenia, and it has been shown that 60% of people with schizophrenia exhibit clinically significant levels of fatigue. Furthermore, 74% experience disturbances in their diurnal activities due to the symptom, affecting their health behaviours (Waters et al., 2013). Fatigue is also associated to reduced quality of life (Zou et al., 2020), and it has been shown that psychiatric conditions were highly associated to important and unexplained fatigue, inducing autonomy loss in patients' lives (Skapinakis et al., 2000). Despite being an invalidating symptom, research lacks on the management of fatigue, and the strategies tested to this day have been inconclusive (Andrade et al., 2015; Luo et al., 2019; Maguire et al., 2020). However, the absence of effective treatments can be explained in part by the lack of knowledge on fatigue in this population, such as how the symptom is experienced amongst people with schizophrenia.

While the experience of fatigue has not yet been studied in schizophrenia (Mulin et al., 2022), several studies using qualitative designs have been conducted in other chronic conditions, such as multiple sclerosis, heart failure or COPD (Jaime-Lara et al., 2020; Whitehead et al., 2016). Qualitative approaches allow better understanding of the lived experience of fatigue amongst these patients, and its consequences on their daily lives. In these populations, studies have shown that fatigue could deteriorate quality of life, and was associated to other symptoms, such as sleep, cognitive disorders, and depression. Moreover, participants reported they felt like they were not understood by their loved ones, and feared that they would not be believed, or be perceived negatively (Jaime-Lara et al., 2020). Catastrophism, a cognitive process leading to negatively exaggerate the assessment of a symptom, represents a substantial part of the experience of fatigue in several chronic conditions (Herck et al., 2023; Lulkahatai & Saligan, 2013). Recent research reported increased levels of fatigue catastrophism in schizophrenia, explaining part of the variance of fatigue severity (Laraki et al., 2024), which could suggest an increased experience of this symptom in patients. Plus, interoception abnormalities in schizophrenia, manifesting through decreased interoceptive precision, and altered interoceptive sensitivity (Ardizzi et al., 2016; Jeganathan et al., 2024; Torregrossa et al., 2022; Yao & Thakkar, 2022). Furthermore, the presence of interoceptive disturbances questions patients' ability to distinguish fatigue from other negative symptoms that may have a close construct, such as apathy, lack of motivation, anhedonia or boredom.

Finally, the study of the experience of fatigue has not been studied in psychosocial rehabilitation contexts. However, fatigue has negative consequences on daily activities and

the adoption of health behaviours (Waters et al., 2013), such as engaging in physical activity (Augustin et al., 2026; Firth et al., 2016), and in cystic fibrosis, fatigue is perceived as a barrier to treatment adherence (Eaton et al., 2020). However, psychosocial rehabilitation programmes are key components of patient care directed towards recovery, and the negative consequences of fatigue could be detrimental to rehabilitation, which makes the study of fatigue in this context particularly relevant.

As such, the overall purpose of this research was to explore the lived experience of fatigue of people with schizophrenia engaged in a psychosocial rehabilitation programme. Two secondary objectives were (i) to explore participants' beliefs in differentiating fatigue from other symptoms with a close construct, and (ii) to identify to which causes, symptoms or factors the participants attributed their fatigue.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants

Participants were recruited amongst patients being accompanied in a French psychosocial rehabilitation centre between November 2025 and January 2026. Each participant was engaged in a psychosocial rehabilitation programme. While they were living at the centre for the duration of the rehabilitation, living on site was principally related to precarity or lack of resources (e.g. no apartment, no income, waiting list for a therapeutic apartment or other therapeutic or autonomous housing arrangements) and patients were free to come and go from the clinic on their own each day. The goal of psychosocial rehabilitation was to help individuals to build a satisfying individualized life project and to encourage recovery. Every patient's care was individualized and relied on a multidisciplinary care team of psychiatrists, specialised educators, a psychologist, a neuropsychologist, a psychometrician, an adapted physical activities teacher, a social worker, art therapists and nurses.

Before enrolment, participants were informed about the potential risks and benefits of the study and gave their written consent to partake in it. Information about the study was sent to the curators of participants under protective measures. This study adhered to the standards mentioned in the latest revision of the Declaration of Helsinki and the French ethical rules and the *Méthodologie de Référence MR-004* (MR-004 compliance declared September 11, 2025) and was approved by a national ethics committee (N° IRB: 00012476-2025-30-10-445). The study was registered on the Health Data Hub (N°26149360) and was also pre-registered on the OSF platform (Registration DOI: [10.17605/OSF.IO/RDZ4Q](https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RDZ4Q)).

The inclusion criteria for the study were the following: 18 years old or above, DSM-V diagnosis of schizophrenia, stable medication (i.e. no antipsychotic modification at least 4 weeks before inclusion) and no major depressive episode. Non-inclusion criteria included: antecedents of inflammatory pathology or severe brain trauma, dependence to toxic products such as alcohol, cannabis or other toxic substances other than tobacco at the time of the study, and ongoing electroconvulsive treatment.

Study design

The study was a qualitative observational study. As people with schizophrenia may exhibit alogia (i.e. poverty of speech) as well as paranoia and/or agoraphobia, individual interviews appeared to be the most relevant to our population. They allowed the researcher to

establish a more trusting relationship with the participants and make them feel at ease, ensuring more honest responses.

Data was collected during one single session, where participants first underwent a semi-structured interview exploring their experience of fatigue. To increase transferability of the results, we assessed the trait of fatigue at the end of the interview with the French version of the Multidimensional Fatigue Inventory (MFI-20) (Gentile et al., 2003; Smets et al., 1995), to inform on the heterogeneity of fatigue in the recruited participants.

An interview guide was developed for the semi-structured interviews with the help of a psychiatrist and a researcher specialized in fatigue assessment in various populations and settings, but also by using the existing literature on fatigue experience in other chronic conditions (Jaime-Lara et al., 2020; Whitehead et al., 2016). The interview started with a small introductory section with questions related to the purpose of the study and how the participants were feeling to put them more at ease. It then followed to a second section that consisted of research-related questions, and focused on participants lived experience of fatigue, their ability to differentiate fatigue from other symptoms, and the causes they attributed to their fatigue. The English translation of the research related questions of the interview is available in Table 1; the original and English translated versions of the interview guide are available in the online supplements (Supplementary 1). All the interviews were audio-recorded with a dictaphone (DVT1120, PHILIPS, the Netherlands) and conducted by the same researcher, that already had experience in conducting semi-structured interviews. To reduce potential stress amongst participants as they could exhibit anxiety and/or social difficulties, the researcher was already known by the participants prior to the study, as she was also involved in the centre's physical activity programme. This increased likelihood of more honest and constructed responses.

We assessed severity of schizophrenia in participants with the French translation of the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (Kay et al., 1987; Lançon et al., 1997), and functional impact of schizophrenia with the Global Assessment of Functioning (American Psychiatric Association, 1994). Medication was also recorded, and antipsychotics were expressed as olanzapine equivalent (Leucht et al., 2020).

Age, height and weight were retributed in participants medical records, and body mass index was derived from the data.

Sampling strategy and sample size calculation

As our purpose was to describe broadly the experience of fatigue in people with schizophrenia, convenience sampling was used to recruit a representative sample of the population under study.

Data collection stopped when reaching saturation, described by Guest et al. (2020) as “the point during data analysis at which incoming data points (interviews) produce little or no new useful information relative to the study objectives”. As suggested by Guest and al. (2020), a base size of 5 interviews and a run length of 3 interviews was used to assess saturation, and saturation was reached when the new information threshold was 5% or less. To build the base size, the number of distinct subcategories found in the interviews composing the base set were assessed. To calculate saturation, the number of new information found in the three interviews of the first run (i.e. new information compared to the information found in the base interviews)

was used. Then, depending on the level of saturation, interviews were added and analysed one-by-one following the above method, until saturation was reached.

Data analysis

We applied a descriptive generic qualitative research method as defined in Sandelowski (2000).

It is important to point out that the terms “content area”, “occurrence” and “meaning unit” are frequently used interchangeably in the literature to refer to the elements of interest identified in interviews. However, to enhance clarity, we have chosen to exclusively use “meaning unit” in this article.

Prior to analysis, the raw data (audio of the interviews) was transcribed ad verbatim by the researcher that led the interviews. We followed a denaturalized transcription approach to facilitate comprehension of the text and focus on the discourse content (Nascimento & Steinbruch, 2019) and grammar, accents or non-standard speeches were corrected and standardized, resulting in a cleaner data (Oliver et al., 2005) for the analysis.

Then, for the primary analysis, each transcription was analysed separately by two researchers and authors of the article. They first reread the interview transcriptions to fully immerse in data, then they identified meaning units in each interview using a coding scheme that was data derived: codes were generated from the data itself during the analysis. They looked for elements in the interview transcripts that answered the research questions (See Table 1). Once each researcher had analysed the transcripts, their analysis was pooled. In the case of a disagreement, they exchanged until the conflict was resolved, and a third author was asked to help reach consensus if needed. Then, all meaning units were sorted into clusters, that were later coded as subcategories and regrouped in broader categories depending on their differences and similarities. This primary analysis was first done on the 8 interviews necessary to the first assessment of saturation (five interviews to build the base size, and three for the first run)., and then on each additional interview until saturation.

Once saturation was reached, a final analysis occurred with all the authors. The purpose of this analysis was to attain a consensus on a complete and comprehensive classification of the meaning units that were identified in the transcripts. Themes were then identified. Finally, as some elements might be considered more important than others by being spoken by multiple participants, we chose to complete this qualitative analysis by quantifying the number of times the identified elements were mentioned.

The app Qualcoder (ver. 3.7) was used during the content analysis. For the participants characteristics (mean \pm standard deviation or median (interquartile range (IQR))) were made using excel (ver. 16.106).

EXPERIENCE AND PERCEPTION OF FATIGUE

What is fatigue for you?

Have you ever felt, either now or in the past, that you were lacking energy or were very tired?

When do you feel this fatigue?

Do you think there are different types of fatigue?

How would you describe this tiredness/lack of energy if you had to explain it to someone?

When you are tired, do you think your tiredness will eventually subside?

What are the consequences of this fatigue?

How do you manage your fatigue on a daily basis?

Are there things that help you reduce/manage your fatigue?

DISTINGUISHING FATIGUE FROM OTHER SYMPTOMS

Do you feel that some of the symptoms you experience could be confused with fatigue?

How do you distinguish your fatigue from other symptoms you might experience on a daily basis?

Do you think there is a difference between 'X' and fatigue? (*Suggested symptoms if not mentioned: sedation, apathy, depression, lack of motivation, emotional numbness, memory or attention problems*)

CAUSES OF FATIGUE

In your opinion, what might contribute to/cause your fatigue?

When you are tired, are there things that can make your fatigue worse?

Table 1. Main research questions

RESULTS

Using a base size of five interviews and a run length of three, saturation was reached at 9⁺, where the three interviews of the last run added 3.75% of new information, reaching the 5% new information threshold determined for saturation in our study. The twelve interviews were analysed; the detailed characteristics of each participant are displayed in Table 2. The mean duration of the interviews was 34.5 minutes (± 11.5). Participants were mainly male ($n=9$), mean age was 36 years (± 6.5), and mean body mass index was 27.5 kg.m⁻² (± 5), with 8 participants being overweight or obese. All participants took antipsychotic medication, with a mean dose in olanzapine equivalent of 20 mg (± 11), and 5 participants also took benzodiazepines. Mean PANSS assessment was 63.5 (± 13.4) and mean GAF score was 46.8 (± 11.0). Finally, the mean total fatigue score at the MFI-20 was 68.4 (± 16.6).

Table 2: Participants characteristics

N°	Interview duration (min)	Sex	Age (years)	BMI (kg/m ²)	SCZ characterization		Treatment			Total fatigue
					PANSS total	GAF	N° of a-psy	Dose eq. Ola (mg)	Benzo.	
1	28.59	Male	40	35.06	92	38	1	7.5	No	60
2	25.45	Male	34	28.93	45	62	1	4.8	No	33

3	26.19	Male	30	22.98	65	41	2	16.5	No	48
4	59.33	Female	27	30.96	56	55	1	9.5	No	73
5	46.32	Female	32	29.74	82	32	2	26.1	No	85
6	20.31	Female	26	31.24	49	60	1	17.8	No	72
7	26.22	Male	40	28.22	58	41	3	39.9	Yes	78
8	39.46	Male	39	33.28	62	45	1	13.1	Yes	83
9	41.17	Male	42	19.52	74	34	2	19.8	Yes	74
10	32.13	Male	35	21.07	58	38	2	20.9	Yes	60
11	43.59	Male	46	22.55	57	60	2	26.1	No	63
12	25.4	Male	43	26.48	64	55	2	37.8	Yes	92

a-psy: antipsychotic; *Benzo.*: benzodiazepines; *BMI*: body mass index; *eq. Ola*: antipsychotic olanzapine equivalence; *GAF*: Global Assessment of Functioning; *gen.*: generation; *PANSS*: Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale

In accordance with the research questions, our findings were divided into three main classifications: the first classification referred to the experience of fatigue (Table 3), the second to the factors participants believed caused their fatigue (Table 4), and the third to participants' ability to distinguish fatigue from symptoms whose constructs could be close to fatigue (Table 5). In total, 598 meaning units were identified in the interviews and classified. As a matter of concision, all the details of the results are not displayed in the results section: while the most mentioned categories in each classification are illustrated by participants quotes, the detailed classifications are available in tables 3 to 5, and all participants citations are available in the supplementary materials (Supplementary 2, Tables 1, 2 and 3).

Experience of fatigue

The experience of fatigue regrouped 372 meaning units, and we identified three main themes: descriptions of fatigue, consequences of fatigue on daily living, and fatigue management strategies. The detailed classification is available in Table 3.

Descriptions of fatigue

Descriptions of fatigue were divided into four main categories: beliefs about fatigue, manifestations of fatigue, qualification of fatigue and variations in fatigue intensity. Beliefs about fatigue were mainly revolving around fatigue catastrophism or the absence of it, where participants were either hoping that fatigue would end up going away “*There may be hope that it will get better in the future*” (P9), or thinking fatigue will always be there “*But fatigue is something you can't really do much about.*” (P5). Participants also distinguished mental fatigue from physical fatigue “*There is psychological fatigue also, it's not just physical fatigue*” (P12), and attributed specific definitions to these two types of fatigue: “*mental [fatigue] is when I don't have clear thoughts*” (P1), “*[physical fatigue] is a physical state that the body has endured and needs to eliminate*” (P2). Finally, some participants believed fatigue could be good “*Eating well, sleeping well, perhaps reading a book—these things are important. They generate good fatigue.*” (P3), or bad “*Bad fatigue is when you haven't slept all night, I think. And when you sit around thinking and don't do anything, don't get on with your day.*” (P3).

The interviews revealed that fatigue manifestation were diverse: many participants reported sensations associated with fatigue, such as feelings of being worn out *“I would say that I am, I am worn out, basically. It's kind of like wear and tear, because when I was a kid, I wasn't like that.”* (P7), heaviness *“There's a weight. There's a heaviness, everything's hard... I don't know, it's hard.”* (P1), effort *“For me, fatigue is when you have put in effort”* (P9), *“It is having to make an effort to do normal things.”* (P7). Sensations also included feeling need for sleep *“It's when you think about the night, right, even though it's morning.”* (P12), *“It's just that our brains, my eyes, they're all heavy, they all want to shut down.”* (P4). Fatigue could also manifest through increased symptoms of schizophrenia: *“I'm feeling unsteady, I don't know if it's a bit of paranoia or what”* (P10).

Participants described fatigue as being tedious *“My brain says, ‘Oh, I'm too tired, I can't, I can't get out of bed.’ That's it, it's very embarrassing.”* (P4), and most of them also qualified the symptom as something that was always there and they had to live with: *“It's part of my routine now, in fact, part of my everyday life.”* (P3), *“It is always there”* (P5). Fatigue was often described as being subsequent to an occupation *“After the activities I did during the day.”* (P3). Finally, participants felt variations in their fatigue, mainly throughout the day, with difficulties in the morning after waking up *“In the morning, just after waking up, like everyone else, I am very, very, very tired.”* (P4), and around midday, after lunch *“At lunchtime, things start to get a bit complicated. Well, not complicated, but I'm a bit less sharp, let's say.”* (P6).

Consequences of fatigue on daily living

Participants described a negative impact of fatigue on their daily activities, where the symptom constituted a barrier mainly in maintaining routines *“It's very, very, very hard to carry on with the rest of my daily routine.”* (P4), to perform desired activities, activities in general *“I don't have a lot of time to act, to do things.”* (P8), and physical activity *“Because of physical fatigue, yes, I don't do any sports”* (P7). Another evidence of this negative impact on activities was the need for participants to spend time resting, impeding other activities: *“I spend a lot of time in my bed”* (P5), *“I'm too tired for that, so I rather rest instead”* (P3). Fatigue also represented a barrier to participants' autonomy outside of the clinic premises: *“I don't go to the village as often as I used to.”* (P10), and could lead to cognitive disorders *“The fact that I'm so overloaded... I just can't think straight.”* (P7).

Fatigue management strategies

Different strategies were used to manage fatigue in participants. First, participants tried to decrease their fatigue or to regain energy, mainly by consuming coffee or other caffeinated beverages: *“I'll get a Monster from Carrefour and drink it, that way... my energy levels go up a bit.”* (P2), even if this strategy was not always considered effective by those implementing it: *“Coffee doesn't really wake me up much anymore.”* (P9). Resting by taking a nap *“I usually have a little nap after lunch, in the afternoon”* (P3), or taking time to relax *“I sit down on... I sit down on a chair and... I sit still.”* (P1) were also used by participants to recover.

The second strategy consisted in distracting themselves from fatigue, by doing cognitive activities *“I do Sudoku puzzles or mental exercises.”* (P3), physical activities *“When I exercise, I feel that my muscles, my body are much lighter.”* (P4), or more passive activities such as listening to music or watching a movie *“When I'm enjoying listening to music or watching a film, I stop thinking about fatigue, you know.”* (P7). Some participants mentioned they just had to keep busy *“The key is to keep yourself busy, to not sit around doing nothing.”* (P5).

Finally, some participants just ignored their fatigue *“I do things without paying attention to fatigue.”* (P11), or used pacing strategies to save energy, by establishing routines or planning their activity and resting periods *“I’ve adopted a schedule to manage this fatigue, a timetable.”* (P3).

Causes of fatigue

The experience of fatigue regrouped 122 meaning units into a single theme, referring to the factors causing fatigue according to the participants. The main categories in this theme were schizophrenia, social factors, psychological factors, physiological factors, (in)activity and unknown causes. The detailed classification is available in Table 4.

Many participants considered schizophrenia or factors associated to the disease were causing fatigue. First, more than half of the participants considered their treatments were causing fatigue. Despite understanding the positive effects of antipsychotics on their pathology, participants considered fatigue was an adverse effect of their medication *“It treats my illness, but it also deprives me of my energy for the whole day.”* (P3), *“I’ve never felt as tired as I have since I started this treatment.”* (P1). Then, a third of the participants thought fatigue was inherent to schizophrenia and was a symptom of their illness *“I think it’s part of schizophrenia.”* (P11), *“Yes, I think it could be a symptom [of schizophrenia].”* (P3). Symptoms of schizophrenia, such as hallucinations *“Having hallucinations, it exhausts me psychologically.”* (P7) were also mentioned by some participants. Participants also reported that their life course associated with the illness, such as frequent hospitalizations also caused fatigue *“And I have been hospitalized for years. [...] So, I think it wears me down more than a normal person.”* (P7).

Then, both activity and inactivity were identified by majority of the participants as causing fatigue. Carrying routines and daily living *“But the whole daily routine is very, very, very tiring”* (P4) as well as having to make an effort were fatiguing for participants *“I put energy into these activities. And it took a lot of effort. So, afterwards, I feel tired.”* (P3). On the other hand, doing nothing was also tiring for participants, and they felt that inactivity led to fatigue *“[...] doing nothing is a vicious circle: I’m exhausted, but without doing anything.”* (P5), *“The less effort you put in, the more tired you get – that’s certain too.”* (P9).

Social factors could also contribute to fatigue, and both social interactions *“Coming across lots of people all day long.”* (P3) and the lack of entourage *“The absence of family, family for a decade”* (P9) could be tiring for the participants. Psychological factors such as guilt *“Guilt is an energy drain, too.”* (P9), stress or depression *“It’s depression.”* (P1) were also identified as causing fatigue. Physiological factors included aging *“I feel that the older I get, the more tired I am.”* (P11), physical illness and sleep disorders *“The fact that I suffer from insomnia.”* (P3). Finally, some participants had difficulties identifying what could cause their fatigue *“I don’t know where this fatigue comes from.”* (P4).

Fatigue and other symptoms

Finally, the third classification synthesized participants’ ability to distinguish fatigue from symptoms whose constructs could be close to fatigue. One hundred and four meaning units were divided between two themes: distinctions between fatigue and other symptoms, and similarities and and/or confusions between fatigue and other symptoms. During this part

of the interview, participants were first asked if they felt that fatigue could be mistaken for other symptoms they experienced. Then, they were questioned on the differences and similarities between fatigue and a list of symptoms with a close construct, if they experienced said symptoms. The detailed classification is available in Table 5.

The symptoms that were considered the most distinct from fatigue for the participants were depression (“*Fatigue is mild compared to depression.*” (P5)), sedation (“*Sedation comes from the effects of the medication. And fatigue is everything else.*” (P6)), amotivation (“*Lack of motivation is like saying, ‘I could do that, but at the same time, I don’t feel like it; I want to rest.’ But fatigue is ‘I can’t.’*” (P4)) and cognitive disorders (“*Fatigue isn’t to blame, so to speak; it’s not always the case – it can happen – but it isn’t always to blame for our memory lapses*” (P6)). At the same time, these were also the symptoms participants thought were difficult to separate from fatigue. Indeed, they mentioned that amotivation (“*If you don’t realise [amotivation] is a symptom, you might well just think you’re tired*” (P11)), sedation (“*The medication was making me feel sedated, and I felt as though I was fatigued.*” (P2)), depression (“*When I’m feeling depressed, I’m mentally exhausted.*” (P10)) and cognitive disorders (more specifically attention disorders: “*Fatigue can cause attention problems, I think*” (P2)) were particularly similar to the manifestations of fatigue. Participants also reported difficulties to dissociate fatigue from negative symptoms: “*Negative symptoms may resemble fatigue.*” (P11). On top of these symptoms, laziness was spontaneously mentioned by some participants, that reported difficulties to differentiate it from fatigue “*Laziness, fatigue – sometimes it’s complicated.*” (P6).

DISCUSSION

In this research, we investigated the experience of fatigue in people with schizophrenia following a qualitative approach. Twelve interviews were analysed and used to build a comprehensive description of fatigue in people with schizophrenia in a psychosocial rehabilitation context. Our results showed that fatigue in people with schizophrenia manifests mainly through sensations such as heaviness, need for sleep and effort. Fatigue in participants was severe and persistent, and while the symptom’s intensity varied throughout the day, participants did not seem to consider that fatigue was unpredictable. As such, some participants spontaneously adopted pacing strategies to manage the symptom. As in other chronic conditions, fatigue’s main repercussions were that the symptom represented a barrier to patients’ everyday occupations and resulted in a significant amount of time spent resting. Most of the strategies used to manage fatigue fell into two categories: trying to regain energy and distracting oneself from fatigue by being busy. Finally, when the participants were asked to dissociate fatigue from other symptoms, interoceptive difficulties arose, as they were able to differentiate the symptoms on a conceptual level, but found them arduous to dissociate on a more perceptive level.

Manifestations of fatigue

Participants described fatigue as a symptom manifesting through a variety of sensations, mainly feelings of heaviness, being worn out, effort and need for sleep. This fatigue is not fully alleviated by sleep or rest, as majority of the participants mentioned that fatigue, while not necessarily being debilitating, was always present. Previous research has considered

that chronic fatigue is a level of trait fatigue where the symptom interferes with one's usual or desired activities (Skau et al., 2021). These manifestations of fatigue might be in favour of considering that the symptom exhibited in schizophrenia is chronic. Still, this should be confirmed through a longitudinal study as some authors have considered that fatigue must be present for at least six months to be considered chronic (Jason et al., 2010).

Fatigue was also described as appearing following an effort or an occupation. Fatigue had negative repercussions on participants' autonomy in daily living and represented a barrier to their daily activities, such as maintaining routines, exercising, or engaging in more creative activities. This is consistent with previous research that showed that fatigue in severe mental illness had a negative impact on diurnal activities (Waters et al., 2013), and could represent a barrier to physical activity (Augustin et al., 2026; Firth et al., 2016). Participants also felt they did less during the day in comparison to the period before they became fatigued, and that a great deal of their time was spent resting or being inactive because they were too tired. Thus, fatigue is impeding patients' occupations, and as such it represents a barrier to their recovery as it prevents them from leading a fulfilling life. These descriptions of fatigue and its impact on daily living are similar to what patients described in other conditions, such as heart failure, multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (Jaime-Lara et al., 2020). In these conditions, fatigue manifested through prolonged tiredness and heaviness, and resulted in difficulties with daily tasks and routines (Jaime-Lara et al., 2020). Moreover, the levels of fatigue assessed with the MFI-20 were particularly high in our participants. With a mean total score of 68, our sample's fatigue reached the 90th percentile, meaning that the level of fatigue exhibited was higher than 90% of the general population (Westenberger et al., 2022). Even for the two participants with relatively lower fatigue scores in comparison to the rest of the sample (33 and 48), fatigue scores still reached the 66th and 86th percentile of the normative values for their sex and age (Westenberger et al., 2022).

Interestingly, while in other chronic conditions patients spoke of how they felt that their fatigue was misunderstood by health care-givers, family and even strangers (Jaime-Lara et al., 2020), it was not the case in our sample. This could be explained by the fact that as participants were engaged in a psychosocial rehabilitation process and were living on-site, they were surrounded by patients that might have a similar experience of the symptom and a care staff accustomed to work with them. While they still encountered people who did not experience fatigue when going outside of the clinic premises, or visiting their families, this represented a short amount of time in their daily living, which could explain why the social burden of fatigue was not particularly important in our sample. Finally, it may appear that some participants exhibited fatigue-related catastrophism, as they did not think that their fatigue would eventually go away. This is consistent with previous findings that showed that fatigue catastrophism contributed to the variance of fatigue severity in people with schizophrenia, and suggested that including fatigue catastrophizing in behavioural interventions could be beneficial (Laraki et al., 2024). Still, participants hoped that fatigue would eventually disappear.

Managing fatigue

When discussing strategies to manage fatigue, participants reported trying to decrease fatigue, distracting oneself from it by keeping busy or using pacing strategies to keep up with daily living. Another method, if it can be considered as such, was ignoring the symptom.

While both mental and physical inactivity and activity were used by participants to regulate their fatigue, these were also identified as causes of fatigue, which appears paradoxical. However, being physically inactive can lead into a downward spiral of fatigue. Indeed, inactivity can lead to a decrease in physical fitness, resulting in a depletion in physical resources and increased fatigability. In this case, people must invest more of their resources to complete a given task, leading to increased fatigue. This is probably the case in schizophrenia, as it has been shown that people with schizophrenia exhibit higher sedentary behaviours and physical inactivity than healthy controls (Soundy et al., 2013; Stubbs et al., 2016; Vancampfort, Firth, et al., 2017), and show impaired physical fitness (Nygård et al., 2019; Vancampfort, Rosenbaum, et al., 2017). Consequently, being active may become tiring because it may deplete the small resources patients have, making them more susceptible to acute fatigue in their daily occupations. Then, frequent resting becomes necessary to restore patients' levels of energy. At the same time, becoming gradually more active and accepting to experience acute fatigue could lead to reduced fatigue on the long term, by increasing resources and building fatigue tolerance (Gruet, 2018). Physical activity practice has for example proven to be useful to decrease fatigue in different chronic conditions exhibiting fatigue, such as cancer (Fakhraei et al., 2022; Kessels et al., 2018) or multiple sclerosis (Oken et al., 2004; Pilutti et al., 2013), where it has been hypothesized that improvement in fatigue levels were linked to an increase in physical fitness. Given the characteristics of people with schizophrenia, the use of physical activity as a strategy to manage fatigue warrants further investigation. On a more psychological side, although participants distinguished amotivation or depression from fatigue on a conceptual level, they explained they experienced difficulties to discriminate them in practice, which is what we suspected given the interoceptive disorders found in this population (Ardizzi et al., 2016; Jeganathan et al., 2024; Torregrossa et al., 2022; Yao & Thakkar, 2022). In this case, confusing amotivation for fatigue can lead to misplaced fatigue management strategies, resulting in inactivity in participants.

Participants also mentioned pacing strategies to manage fatigue, which is interesting as these can be found in other chronic conditions experiencing fatigue, especially in Myalgic Encephalomyelitis Chronic Fatigue Syndrome (ME/SFC), where people are encouraged to be active while respecting the limits imposed by their condition. This often translates by planning and alternating active and resting moments to avoid increases in fatigue (Sanal-Hayes et al., 2023), which has shown positive effects on fatigue in ME/SCF (Sanal-Hayes et al., 2025). Since no participant mentioned that their fatigue was fluctuating in a non-previsible manner, pacing strategies could be anticipated if they were to be implemented. As some participants spontaneously integrated pacing in their lifestyle, it could be interesting to investigate its potential use in schizophrenia. Importantly, while there is ongoing debate in ME/CFS regarding the effectiveness of traditional graded physical activity, this is not the case in schizophrenia, where post-exertional malaise is not a concern. Therefore, there is no justification for discouraging engagement in conventional graded physical activity. Pacing, or more broadly self-regulated physical activity, should thus instead be considered as a potentially complementary approach, which may introduce flexibility and variability in intervention strategies.

Our participants also reported daily variations in their fatigue, with higher levels of fatigue in the mornings and around midday, and weekly variations with fatigue accumulating over the course of the week. While the reported accumulation of fatigue through the course of the week is similar to what has been found in the general population, the daily variations of

fatigue reported by our participants contrast with findings from the general population, where fatigue accumulates progressively throughout the day (Micklewright et al., 2017). These findings may have practical implications, particularly for physical activity interventions, by highlighting specific time windows during which engagement may be more favourable. Given that fatigue is known to reduce intention to exert effort (Brown & Bray, 2019), and consequently the likelihood of engaging in vigorous physical activity, targeting periods of lower fatigue may help optimize participation, engagement and adherence.

Causes of fatigue and differentiating fatigue from other symptoms

One cause of fatigue that was frequently given by participants was schizophrenia itself, where participants considered that fatigue was inherent to the illness, and a symptom of it. This is particularly interesting, as it may refer to primary fatigue, a concept frequently used in research on fatigue in clinical settings. Primary fatigue is defined as fatigue for which the sole explanatory factor is the illness itself and is often associated with inflammation (Radbruch et al., 2008). In addition to this concept, researchers also identify secondary fatigue, is explained by other factors in the individual's life, such as their lifestyle, risk factors and comorbidities (Radbruch et al., 2008). Our results support this view, as participants also attributed their fatigue to secondary factors, such as aging, physical illness, sleep quality, antipsychotic treatment, activity and inactivity, and further quantitative research should be led to explore whether this dichotomy is applicable in schizophrenia.

Attributing fatigue to aging and physical illness can be explained by the fact that people with schizophrenia are less likely to consult their healthcare professionals for somatic care (Hausleiter et al., 2021; Oud & Meyboom-de Jong, 2009). Consequently, opportunities for preventing comorbidities and managing consequences of aging and illnesses are reduced, contributing to poorer physical health among patients, which could contribute to fatigue. Offering a physical health check to people with schizophrenia complaining of fatigue could therefore be a way of determining whether certain factors or comorbidities might be affecting participants' health and contributing to their fatigue.

Almost all participants considered that their treatments, mainly antipsychotics, could be a cause of fatigue, which could be an adverse effect of the medication. However, antipsychotics also exhibit sedative properties, with varying intensity depending on the substance (Huhn et al., 2019), and benzodiazepines, that were taken by 5 of our participants, are also sedative. Given that participants stated they had difficulties to separate sedation from fatigue, as they can manifest through similar sensations, it is possible that they confused fatigue with the sedative effect of their medication. This is substantiated by a recent systematic review and meta-analysis on fatigue associations in psychosis that showed low prevalence of antipsychotic-related fatigue, and hypothesized that fatigue and sedation may be independent side effects of antipsychotics (Poole-Wright et al., 2025). Plus, participants mentioned that fatigue started when they began taking medication, during the early stages of their illness. However, this period of their life coincided with a sudden change in their habits, and some participants hypothesized that it was the rupture with their lifestyle before the onset of the illness rather than just the medication that caused fatigue. Still, the relationships between fatigue, sedation and antipsychotic medication should be investigated further as they could provide a more comprehensive framework of fatigue in people treated with these medications. Furthermore, part of sedative effects of antipsychotics could be managed by taking them at

night, and selecting treatments best tolerated by patients (Stroup & Gray, 2018). Finally, even if the ability to differentiate sedation from fatigue may not directly help patients to manage these symptoms, psychoeducation could help patients identify their sensations and better understand bodily signals.

Finally, while participants were able to tell physical fatigue from mental fatigue, discriminating fatigue from other symptoms, such as laziness, amotivation, cognitive disorders and depression proved to be difficult. Majority of these difficulties were not mentioned spontaneously, and it was arduous for participants to give more details about this topic. This could be attributed to the fact that participants might not have been asked if some of the symptoms they experienced could be similar to fatigue before this study, and the interoceptive abnormalities witnessed in schizophrenia (Ardizzi et al., 2016; Jeganathan et al., 2024; Torregrossa et al., 2022; Yao & Thakkar, 2022). As assessing bodily states and determining the causes of said state is difficult in people with schizophrenia, they may confuse symptoms with similar manifestations. This could lead to incorrectly attributing fatigue to bodily sensations, resulting in inadequate strategies in response. As such, learning to discriminate fatigue from laziness, amotivation, cognitive disorders and depression through psychoeducation may help patients adopt the appropriate behaviour depending on what they are feeling. Furthermore, research should allow more in-depth exploration of the confusion of fatigue with other symptoms, as it might provide insight on interoceptive abnormalities in schizophrenia, and help understand the potential overlaps between these different concepts.

Study limits

There are several limitations to this study, that may be related to the context of the study and the population under study, as well as methodological bias. First, our participants were relatively young, with ages ranging from 26 to 46 and a mean age of 36. While this is common in a social rehabilitation context, our findings might not be transferable to older people with schizophrenia. The sex-ratio of our sample was uneven, as only a quarter of our participants were female (n=3), which can be a limiting factor to the transferability of our results to a more homogenous sample, especially considering the sex ratio is more balanced in schizophrenia (male/female ratio = 1.1, (Solmi et al., 2023)). Furthermore, based on PANNS and GAF assessments and severity cutoffs, symptom severity was mild to moderate (Leucht et al., 2005), and functional impairment was serious in our participants; our findings might not be transferable to people with higher symptom severity, or different levels of functional impairment. Finally, generalisability to people undergoing an acute episode or having unstable medication is limited as these were part of our exclusion criteria.

As *alogia* is a symptom of schizophrenia, language was poor in some participants. In addition, they could also exhibit memory deficits and cognitive difficulties. As a result, certain meaning units were difficult to interpret, due to lack of precisions. When participants were asked to develop further during the interviews, they often had difficulties to give more information to the researcher, which could lead to frustration. To prevent this and increase trustworthiness, the researcher frequently summarized what the participant had said during the interview and asked for confirmation, reformulated questions as many times as necessary to ensure he was understood, and made sure that all terms were comprehended, defining them if needed. To minimise interpretative bias in our classification process, we opted for manifest content analysis classify to select meaning units, and classified them solely based on

participant's verbatim, which helped avoid potential influence of our personal values and beliefs. Plus, while all the interviews were led and transcribed by the same researcher, the identification of the meaning units and the construction of the preliminary classifications were done by two authors, and the final classification resulted in a consensus between all four authors. Finally, the context of psychosocial rehabilitation is a particular setting, and it is possible that manifestations of fatigue may be different in other settings, such as people with schizophrenia with unstable medication or an acute episode, or people in community or autonomous living conditions. Indeed, while a few of our participants mentioned that their fatigue appeared with the onset of schizophrenia, no research has confirmed the temporal characteristics of fatigue in schizophrenia using a longitudinal study design to this date. In lupus for example, research has shown that people felt that fatigue was worse during exacerbation of their disease (Cleanthous et al., 2021). It is thus not guaranteed that the experience of fatigue of our participants is universal to every individual diagnosed with schizophrenia.

Conclusion

In conclusion, fatigue in schizophrenia is high and persistent, and manifests mainly through sensations such as heaviness, need for sleep and effort. While fatigue has varying intensity through the day, participants do not seem to define it as non-previsible, and as such, pacing strategies such as the ones used in ME/SCF may be of interest in schizophrenia. As in other chronic conditions, fatigue results in a consequent amount of time spent resting and represents a barrier to patients' everyday occupations, impeding the psychosocial rehabilitation process. Most of the strategies used to manage fatigue fall into two categories: trying to regain energy and distracting oneself from fatigue by being busy. Finally, it is important to note that the interoceptive abnormalities exhibited in schizophrenia also manifest when trying to dissociate fatigue from depression, amotivation, sedation and laziness, which highlights the importance for them to learn to identify these different elements, which could result in a better evaluation and management of fatigue.

While our study allowed us to better understand fatigue in schizophrenia in the context of psychosocial rehabilitation, objective research on the correlates of fatigue in patients should be led to complete our findings with quantitative information. Studies investigating the potential effect of therapeutic fatigue management strategies such as pacing, physical activity or psychoeducational interventions focusing on fatigue catastrophism and interoception should be carried out in order to ultimately reduce the burden of fatigue and improve patients' quality of life.

Table 3: Experience of fatigue in people with schizophrenia

Themes	Main categories	Categories	Sub-categories	Participants per category (%)	
Descriptions of fatigue	Beliefs about fatigue	Fatigue catastrophism	Hope about the temporary nature of fatigue	41.7	
			Fatalism about the immutable nature of fatigue	41.7	
		Distinction between good and bad fatigue			16.7
		Distinction between physical and mental fatigue	Differences in physical and mental fatigue	50	
			Similarities between physical and mental fatigue	33.3	
			Specificities of mental fatigue	66.7	
			Specificities of physical fatigue	58.3	
		Manifestations of fatigue	Sensations	Pain	8.3
				Slowness	16.7
				Heaviness	50
	Sluggishness			16.7	
	Stiffness			8.3	
	Being worn out			33.3	
	Lack of energy			16.7	
	Lack of envy			16.7	
	Sleep			58.3	
	Effort			58.3	
	Dissociation			33.3	
	Increased symptoms of schizophrenia		Positive symptoms	8.3	
		Negative symptoms	16.7		
	Qualification of fatigue	Persistence		75	
		Subsequent to an occupation		33.3	
		Tediousness		33.3	
Variations in fatigue intensity	Increased fatigue post treatment		16.7		
	Daily variations	More fatigue in the mornings	41.7		
		Less fatigue in the mornings	25		
		More fatigue around midday	33.3		
		More fatigue at the end of the day	16.7		
	Weekly variations		8.3		
Variations related to brightness		16.7			
Consequences of fatigue on	Negative impact on activities	Less activities compared to the period before fatigue		33.3	
		Barrier to physical activity		50	
		Barriers to routines		41.7	

		Barrier to performing desired activities	25	
		Barriers to crafting activities	16.7	
		Barriers to activities in general	41.7	
		Time spent inactive/resting	50	
	Barrier to autonomy outside of the institution		25	
	Barrier to social interactions		16.7	
	Decreased enjoyment		8.3	
	Slowing		25	
	Cognitive disorders		25	
Fatigue management strategies	Decreasing fatigue/ increasing energy	Consuming something	Caffeine consumption	50
			Other	25
		Resting	Sleeping	33.3
			Taking a nap	33.3
			Taking time to rest/relax	41.7
		Beneficial effect of treatments		16.7
	Spirituality		8.3	
	Distracting oneself from fatigue	Cognitive activities		33.3
		Passive activities		33.3
		Crafting activities		8.3
		Physical activities		33.3
		Forcing oneself to be active		16.7
		Keeping busy		41.7
	Ignoring fatigue		33.3	
	Pacing strategies	Planning activities and rest		16.7
Establishing routines		8.3		

Table 4: Causes of fatigue in people with schizophrenia

Theme	Main categories	Categories	Sub-categories	Participants per category (%)
Factors causing fatigue	Schizophrenia	Treatment		66.7
		Fatigue is a symptom of schizophrenia		33.3
		Positive symptoms	Hallucinations	16.7
			Delusions	8.3
		Negative symptoms	Disorganisation	8.3
			Other symptoms	8.3
		Life course associated with the disease	Frequent hospitalizations	16.7
			Rupture with the pre-schizophrenia lifestyle	8.3

	Social factors	Social interactions are tiring		25
		Lack of social interactions is tiring		25
		Agoraphobia		8.3
	Psychological factors	Stress		16.7
		Depression		16.7
		Guilt		8.3
		Procrastination		8.3
	Physiological factors	Aging		25
		Physical illness		16.7
		Sleep disorders	Sleep quality	16.7
			Insomnia	8.3
	(in)activity	Making an effort		58.3
		Doing nothing		50
Daily living/routines		33.3		
Unknown causes			16.7	

Table 5: Distinction between fatigue and other symptoms in people with schizophrenia

Themes	Main categories	Categories	Participants per category (%)
Distinction between fatigue and other symptoms	Fatigue is different from amotivation		25
	Fatigue is different from anxiety		8.3
	Fatigue is different from apathy		16.7
	Fatigue is different from depression		50
	Fatigue is different from laziness		16.7
	Fatigue is different from sedation		41.7
	Fatigue is different from cognitive disorders		25
Similarities/confusion between fatigue and other symptoms	Fatigue is similar to amotivation		66.7
	Fatigue is similar to anxiety/fear		8.3
	Fatigue is similar to apathy		8.3
	Fatigue is similar to depression		58.3
	Fatigue is similar to emotional numbness		8.3
	Fatigue is similar to laziness		25
	Fatigue is similar to physical manifestations of illness		8.3
	Fatigue is similar to sedation		66.7
	Fatigue is similar to negative symptoms		25
	Fatigue is similar to cognitive disorders	Memory disorders	16.7
Attention disorders		41.7	
Unspecific cognitive disorders		33.3	

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